

Peer Pressure as Determinant of Examination Integrity in Secondary Schools in Garissa Township Sub County, Kenya

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Abstract.

Examinations are the cornerstone of any education system, playing a critical role in evaluating students' knowledge, skills, and academic progress. Maintaining the integrity of these examinations is paramount to ensure that educational outcomes are both credible and equitable. This research was aimed to investigate how peer pressure is a determinant of examination integrity in secondary schools in Garissa Township Sub County. The study adopted descriptive survey design to investigate how peer pressure is a determinants of examination integrity in secondary schools. It focused on mixed method research approach to combine quantitative and qualitative approaches so as to gather both numerical data on prevalence and in-depth insight. Respondents were sampled using stratified and simple random sampling. There was a sample of 11 schools out of 38 (30% of 38 schools), consisting of 4 boys' schools, 3 girls' schools and 4 mixed schools. Thus 11 Principals were selected using census, 55 teachers and 77 students' representatives were also selected using simple sampling. The data was collected using structured questionnaires for teachers and students' representatives while principals had face to face interviews. Descriptive data was analyzed using frequencies, mean, percentages and pie charts. Inferential statistics, Pearson correlation was used to analyze quantitative data and test hypothesis while qualitative data was analyzed verbatim. Research findings indicated that Peer Pressure was significantly related to examinations integrity It was moderately correlated with level of integrity of examinations ($r=0.446$, $p<.05$). The findings of this study contribute to the existing body of knowledge on examination integrity and unearth how peer pressure contributes to cheating in examinations in secondary schools in Garissa Township sub-county.

Key words: Peer Pressure, Examination, Integrity, Determinant.

1.0 Introduction

Academic integrity refers to the ethical conduct and fairness in the process of administering and evaluating examinations, it is a commitment to fundamental moral values such as honesty, trust, fairness, decency, respect and responsibility (Keohane, 1999). Academic misconduct, including cheating in exams, is a complex issue influenced by various factors, among which peer influence plays a significant role. When peers engage in dishonest practices, it can lead others to justify similar behaviors, creating a culture where academic misconduct becomes normalized or tolerated. Positive peer influence can play a significant role in deterring cheating in exams by creating an environment where academic integrity is valued and upheld. Digital proctoring frameworks can leverage positive peer influence to deter cheating in online exams. For example, the Massive Open Online Proctoring framework developed by Li et al. (2015) includes a Peer Cheating Detector (PCD) that uses peer-based review processes to detect cheating behaviors.

Positive peer influence can play a crucial role in promoting academic integrity and developing intervention strategies to curb academic misconduct. Institutions need to have clear policies for addressing contract cheating and other forms of academic misconduct. Providing a supportive environment where students feel comfortable reporting cases of academic dishonesty among their peers is critical. Ellis, Zucker, and Randall (2018) suggest that policy should include safeguards for false accusations and protection for individuals raising concerns. Peer influence can be tracked throughout student's educational journey and find how they affect different aspects of a student's school life. Steenberghs et al. (2021) explored the impact of different peer groups on individual students' engagement and disengagement throughout an academic year. The study focused on the influence of friends, popular peers, and the entire class, considering emotional and behavioral engagement. The results

indicated that self-esteem and cognitive ability could moderate the effect of peer group norms on individual engagement (Nina et al. 2021). A review of classroom management practices in primary schools by Taylor et al. (2021) examined various disciplinary approaches and their effects on student behavior. The study indicated that changes in classroom management could significantly influence peer relationships and, subsequently, students' engagement and behavior throughout their educational journey.

Research indicates that peer influence plays a significant role in shaping student behavior. When students observe their peers engaging in academic misconduct without facing consequences, they may perceive such behavior as acceptable. According to Jones et al. (2016), peer influence significantly impacts students' decisions to cheat, particularly when they believe that peers who engage in cheating are not penalized. The concept of perceived norms is central to understanding academic misconduct. Several studies have explored strategies to reduce peer-driven cheating. According to Boehm et al. (2009), promoting a culture of academic integrity through educational initiatives can help reduce cheating behaviors. These studies highlight the importance of addressing peer influence and establishing clear consequences for academic misconduct. By promoting a culture of academic integrity and consistently enforcing policies, educational institutions can reduce the likelihood of students cheating when they perceive their peers engaging in similar behaviors without consequences.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The issue of exam malpractices has been a challenge for quite sometimes in Garissa Township Sub-County. The parliamentary departmental committee (2023) report on examination malpractice exposed many cases of cheating in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) examinations in a number of counties including Garissa. However, the report did not give detailed information on the causes of examinations malpractices. The integrity of examinations in secondary schools within the Sub County is facing challenges that pose students credibility on pursuing high level courses like medicine and engineering due to false grades. Addressing these challenges is imperative to ensure a fair, transparent, and credible examination system in secondary schools within Garissa Township Sub County. This study aims to explore how peer pressure is one of the determinants among others contributing to examination integrity, providing insights from Garissa Township sub-county that can inform policies, interventions, and educational practices to safeguard the authenticity of examinations and promote a culture of academic honesty and integrity among students.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study was to establish relationship between peer pressure and examination integrity in secondary schools in Garissa Township Sub County.

1.3 Research Question

To guide the study, this research question was used;

What is the relationship between peer pressure and examination integrity in secondary schools in Garissa Township Sub County?

1.4 Research Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis was used to guide the study:

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between peer pressure and examination integrity in secondary schools in Garissa Township Sub County.

1.5 Theoretical Framework

Social Learning Theory: Social learning theory, as proposed by Albert Bandura (1977), states that humans learn socially not just intellectually, it emphasizes the importance of observing, modeling, and imitating the behaviors, attitudes, and emotional reactions of others, the role of social interactions and observational learning in shaping behavior. Individuals learn from observing the behaviors and attitudes of others in their social environment. In the context of examination integrity, this theory suggests that students may engage in unethical practices if they observe peers or role models doing the same. It emphasizes the importance of peer influence, teacher modeling, and community behavior in understanding determinants of examination integrity. According to Perkins (2003) peer influences are affected more by perceived norms rather than the actual norms. According to the theory, our perceptions of what others accept and expect of us are more often inaccurate and misleading.

The theory thus assumes that our behavior, whether positive or negative is influenced by misperceptions of how our peers think and act. This informs the researcher that students' perception of peers has influence on societal norms among learners (Kirugua 2019).

1.6 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework provided a structured basis for the research that was designed to illustrate the key concepts, variables, and their interrelationships in the context of examination integrity.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

The Conceptual framework was aimed to provide a visual representation of how various factors influence examination integrity in the study area. In this case, peer pressure has significant impact on examination integrity, either positively or negatively. Some principals visit the Sub-County Directors of Education with proposals on their desired supervisors due to pressure from students, they thus levy motivational fees on parents to pay examiners, bribe invigilators, security officers, supervisors, MoE and KNEC officials. (Newsbyte 2022). The claim of insecurity that the insurgent group will attack the KNEC monitors if they go to the interior schools eased the exam malpractices to intensify (CGAB 2020).

2.0 Literature Review

Peer pressure is a significant social factor that can influence students' attitudes and behaviors, including their approach to examination integrity. In secondary schools in Garissa Township Sub County, as in many other settings, the impact of peer pressure on examination integrity is a subject of interest and concern. Several studies have highlighted the influence of peer pressure on examination integrity. Within the context of secondary education, students often spend a considerable amount of time with their peers. The pressure to conform to group norms can lead to behaviors such as cheating and collusion during examinations. Research has shown that students may engage in academic dishonesty to conform to the norms established within their peer groups (Doll et al., 2004). Students who perceive that their peers are engaging in cheating or other unethical practices may feel compelled to do the same in order to fit in or avoid social ostracism. (McCabe et al., 2012). Peer pressure can create a fear of isolation for students who do not engage in unethical practices during examinations. In some cases, students may resort to cheating to maintain their social standing and avoid being labeled as outsiders within their peer groups (Doll et al., 2004)

The concept of reciprocity plays a role in the relationship between peer pressure and examination integrity. Students may feel indebted to their peers for assistance during examinations and may reciprocate by assisting their peers in return. This mutual support can lead to a culture of academic dishonesty (Anderman et al., 1998). The influence of peer pressure is not solely negative. Ethical role models within peer groups can encourage and support ethical behavior during examinations. Students who have friends with strong ethical values are more likely to resist peer pressure to cheat (Storch & Storch, 2003). Students often have a strong sense of identity and belonging within their peer groups. The desire to maintain a positive group identity can either promote ethical behavior (if the group values integrity) or encourage unethical conduct if cheating is normalized (Huang et al., 2013). Social learning theory posits that individuals learn from observing others. Peer influence plays a pivotal role in shaping academic behaviors.

Davis and Ludvigson (1995) found that students are more likely to cheat when they perceive their peers engaging in similar behaviors without consequences. In the cultural context of Garissa Township Sub County, where collectivist norms are prevalent, peer influence might strongly impact candidates' decisions to engage in dishonest practices. Peer pressure exerts a considerable influence on examination integrity in secondary schools in Garissa Township Sub County. It can either encourage ethical behavior or lead students to engage in academic dishonesty, depending on the prevailing norms within their peer groups. Recognizing the importance of peer dynamics and their impact on examination integrity is crucial for developing strategies and interventions to promote a culture of academic honesty among students in the region.

Academic misconduct, including cheating in exams, is a complex issue influenced by various factors, among which peer influence plays a significant role. When peers engage in dishonest practices, it can lead others to justify similar behaviors, creating a culture where academic misconduct becomes normalized or tolerated. A study by Bartolic et al. (2021) explored how students perceived academic misconduct among their peers during the rapid transition to remote instruction due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The results indicated that social desirability bias could be mitigated by focusing on students' beliefs about cheating norms rather than direct questions about their own behaviors. Subjective cheating norms can strongly influence whether or not students cheat, even in institutions with clear academic integrity policies or honor codes. The studies above underscore the importance of addressing peer influence and promoting a culture of academic integrity to prevent academic misconduct and cheating in exams. Educational interventions, ethical leadership, and consistent enforcement of academic integrity policies can play key roles in reducing the impact of peer influence on academic misconduct.

3.0 Research Methodology

Research methodology refers to the systematic approach and set of techniques used to conduct research, gather information, analyze data, and draw conclusions in a scientific and structured manner. Kerlinger (2003) contends that survey design is used to gather data from a large population at a particular time with the intention of describing the current situation. The study therefore adopted a survey research design. It focused on mixed method research approach to combine quantitative and qualitative approaches so as to gather both numerical data on prevalence and in-depth insights into candidates' perceptions, motivations, and contextual factors. Garissa Township Sub County was the geographical location where the research took place. Garissa Township Sub County is located in the northeastern part of Kenya and is known for its unique cultural, social, and economic dynamics. The target population for this research focused on student leaders who are preparing to take the Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) Examinations from various schools in different parts of Garissa Township Sub County. Similarly, teachers who were involved in preparing and guiding candidates for the national examinations who might have insights into academic integrity policies and practices was focused. School principals also provided insights into the school environment and policies related to examinations. The 30% strategy for sampling had been used 30% of N ($30/100 * N$) where N was the total population. There was a sample of 11 schools out of 38 (30% of 38 schools), consisting of 4 boys' schools, 3 girls' schools and 4 mixed schools. Thus 11 Principals were selected using census, 5 teachers from every school (20% of 25 teachers) totaling to 55 teachers and 7 student leaders representatives totaling to 77 students using simple sampling. The research instruments that were used were survey questionnaires administered to teachers and student leaders' representatives and personal interviews was conducted to principals to gather deeper insights into experiences, perspectives, and suggestions related to examination integrity.

3.1 Validity and Reliability of Research Instrument

The research instruments for this study was validated through application of content validity, which was determined by expert judgement for both survey questionnaires and Interviews, the process of establishing validity involved careful planning, expert consultation, pilot testing, and refining the instrument based on feedback. Test-Retest Reliability technique was used to establish the reliability of the instruments. To assess test-retest reliability the instrument was administered to a group of participants. After a week, the same instrument was re-administered to the same group. The correlation between the participants' responses in the two administrations was calculated. A correlation coefficient (r) of about 0.75 was obtained and that was be considered high enough to judge the reliability of the instrument. (Orodho, 2009).

3.2 Data Analysis

Qualitative data was analyzed verbatim while Quantitative data was analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) and descriptive statistics was presented using frequency tables. Research findings indicated that the independent variable was significantly related to the dependent variable. Peer pressure was moderately correlated with level of integrity of examinations ($r=0.446, p<.05$).

4.0 Results

Questionnaires were distributed to teachers and students in 11 high schools within Garissa Sub County. Percentages, means and standard deviations were used to describe the responses of the study participants. The following Tables present the summary of the responses.

Table 1:

Descriptive analysis on peer pressure

	SD	D	N	A	SA
Peer influence contributes to academic misconduct, including cheating in exams.	0.00%	2.30%	12.50%	46.10%	39.10%
Positive peer influence can be used to deter cheating in exams.	0.00%	1.60%	10.90%	62.50%	25.00%
Positive peer influence can be harnessed to develop intervention strategies on academic integrity.	0.80%	2.30%	20.30%	54.70%	21.90%
Changes in peer influence can be tracked throughout student's educational journey.	0.80%	5.50%	24.20%	49.20%	20.30%
Students are more likely to cheat when they perceive their peers engaging in similar behaviors without consequences.	0.80%	3.10%	24.20%	53.10%	18.80%

Source: Researcher (2024)

This Table presents statistical data regarding various statements related to peer influence and its impact on examination integrity in secondary schools within Garissa Township Sub County, Kenya. The table includes percentages representing the distribution of responses across different categories of agreement, namely Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D), Neutral (N), Agree (A), and Strongly Agree (SA). Across the various statements, a consistent pattern can be observed. Firstly, a significant majority of respondents agree or strongly agree that peer influence contributes to academic misconduct, including cheating in exams, with 46.10% agreeing and 39.10% strongly agreeing. Similarly, respondents largely believe in the potential of positive peer influence to deter cheating, with 62.50% agreeing and 25.00% strongly agreeing. Furthermore, a substantial proportion of participants (54.70% agreeing and 21.90% strongly agreeing) perceive positive peer influence as a viable resource for developing intervention strategies on academic integrity. Additionally, there is considerable acknowledgment (49.20% agreeing and 20.30% strongly agreeing) that changes in peer influence can be monitored throughout a student's educational journey. Lastly, the majority of respondents (53.10% agreeing and 18.80% strongly agreeing) concur that students are more inclined to cheat when they perceive their peers engaging in similar behaviors without consequences. These findings collectively suggest a recognition of the significant influence peers wield in shaping academic conduct and the potential for leveraging positive peer dynamics to foster integrity within educational settings.

Table 2:

Mean and standard deviation of peer influence items

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Peer influence contributes to academic misconduct, including cheating in exams.	128	4.22	0.752
Positive peer influence can be used to deter cheating in exams.	128	4.11	0.643
Positive peer influence can be harnessed to develop intervention strategies on academic integrity.	128	3.95	0.767
Changes in peer influence can be tracked throughout student's educational journey.	128	3.83	0.843
Students are more likely to cheat when they perceive their peers engaging in similar behaviors without consequences.	128	3.86	0.781

Source: Researcher 2024

The above Table summarizes the nature of peer influence in academic settings, particularly concerning cheating behaviors during exams. The data reveal a generally high acknowledgment among respondents regarding the significant contribution of peer influence to academic misconduct, as indicated by a mean rating of 4.22 out of 5. This suggests a widespread recognition among students and teachers of the role peers play in shaping behaviors related to cheating. Moreover, the relatively low standard deviation accompanying this result (0.752) indicates a notable level of consensus among respondents. Conversely, while positive peer influence is perceived as a potential deterrent to cheating, with a mean rating of 4.11 and a slightly lower standard deviation (0.643), there appears to be some hesitation or skepticism regarding its effectiveness for intervention purposes, as reflected in the lower mean rating of 3.95 for the item concerning the harnessing of positive peer influence for developing intervention strategies on academic integrity. The higher standard deviation associated with this item (0.767) suggests more variability in responses, implying a divergence of opinions among respondents. Similarly, the feasibility of tracking changes in peer influence throughout a student's educational journey receives a moderate level of agreement (mean rating of 3.83), but with a relatively high standard deviation (0.843), indicating a wider range of perspectives on this matter. Finally, the relationship between students' perceptions of peer behavior and their likelihood of engaging in cheating, particularly in the absence of consequences, elicits a moderate level of agreement (mean rating of 3.86) but with notable variability in responses (standard deviation of 0.781).

Hypothesis

The study hypothesis stated that *there is no significant relationship between peer pressure and the level of integrity of KCSE examinations in high schools in Garissa sub county Kenya*. Pearson correlation coefficient was used to test hypothesis . Table 7 presents the results of the correlation analysis.

Table 3:

Correlation analysis of peer pressure and level of examinations integrity

Variable		Peer pressure	Level of KCSE Examinations Integrity
Peer pressure	Correlation Coefficient	1	.446**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	0
	N	128	128
Level of KCSE Examinations Integrity	Correlation Coefficient	.446**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	.
	N	128	128

Source: Researcher 2024

The correlation analysis examines the relationship between peer pressure and the level of integrity in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) examinations. The results reveal a statistically significant positive correlation coefficient of .446** between these two variables. This indicates that there is a moderate positive relationship between peer pressure and the level of integrity in KCSE examinations. The significance level (Sig. 2-tailed) is reported as 0.000, implying that the observed correlation is highly unlikely to have occurred by chance. This finding suggests that as peer pressure increases, there is a tendency for the level of integrity concern in KCSE examinations to also increase. The correlation analysis gives strong evidence to reject the first hypothesis of the study.

The correlation analysis conducted in this study provides information into the relationship between peer pressure and the level of integrity in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) examinations. The statistically significant positive correlation coefficient of .446** suggests a moderate positive relationship between these two variables, indicating that as peer pressure increases, there is a tendency for the level of integrity concern in KCSE examinations to also increase. This finding challenges the initial hypothesis of the study, suggesting that peer pressure may play a significant role in influencing students' behaviors related to exam integrity.

However, the relationship between peer pressure and exam malpractice appears to be a topic of ongoing debate in recent literature. On one hand, the findings of a 2013 Nigerian study by Okorodudu (2013) suggest a positive correlation between peer pressure and students' willingness to engage in exam malpractice. This implies that pressure from peers can indeed influence students towards cheating, potentially undermining the integrity of examinations. Conversely, a contrasting viewpoint emerges from a 2016 study by Bassey and Iruonje (2016), which found a negative correlation between peer pressure and exam malpractice. Their research suggests that peer pressure might actually discourage students from cheating, indicating the presence of positive peer influence promoting honest test-taking behaviors.

These divergent findings bring to light the complex and nuanced nature of peer pressure dynamics in educational settings and their impact on academic integrity. While the correlation analysis in this study points towards a positive relationship between peer pressure and integrity concern in KCSE examinations, it's essential to acknowledge the potential mitigating factors and contextual nuances that may influence this relationship. Factors such as the nature of peer relationships, school culture, and individual differences in susceptibility to peer influence could all play a role in shaping students' responses to peer pressure in the context of academic integrity.

Additionally, the interviews on the principals indicated that the role of societal pressure and expectations emerged as influential factors contributing to the prevalence of exam malpractice, as highlighted by educational administrators and principals. In discussions surrounding the root causes of academic dishonesty, these stakeholders underscored how the pervasive pressure to excel academically, largely driven by societal norms and expectations, can significantly impact students' ethical decision-making processes. In interviews conducted with school administrators, one principal elaborated on this notion, stating, "The pressure on students to perform well in examinations is immense, and this pressure often translates into unethical behavior, such as cheating." This sentiment was echoed by several other administrators, who emphasized the profound influence of societal expectations on students' attitudes towards academic integrity.

Moreover, the link between academic performance and employability was emphasized as a key contributing factor to the prevalence of exam malpractice. School administrators highlighted how the increasingly competitive job market places a premium on academic achievements, thereby heightening the stakes associated with examination outcomes. As one principal remarked, "In our society, there is a prevailing belief that academic success is directly correlated with employability prospects. As a result, students feel immense pressure to excel in examinations, often resorting to unethical means to secure favorable outcomes." This sentiment underscores the broader socio-economic implications associated with academic performance and the pressures exerted on students to succeed at all costs.

Furthermore, the influence of peer pressure on students' propensity to engage in exam malpractice was a recurring theme in discussions surrounding academic integrity. Administrators and educators alike highlighted how students are susceptible to the behaviors and attitudes of their peers, particularly in high-pressure academic environments. In interviews conducted with school administrators, one principal elaborated on this phenomenon, stating, "Students are more likely to cheat in exams if they perceive their peers engaging in similar behaviors without consequences. The desire to conform to peer norms and expectations can override their moral compass, leading them to compromise their integrity." This observation underscores the powerful influence of peer dynamics on students' ethical decision-making processes and highlights the need for targeted interventions to address peer pressure in educational settings.

5.0 Conclusion

Addressing peer influence in academic misconduct requires a multifaceted approach that involves students, teachers, and institutions working together to promote a culture of integrity and respect. By emphasizing positive peer influence and creating a supportive community, academic institutions can build an environment where cheating is discouraged and academic honesty is valued. By using positive peer influence to develop intervention strategies, academic institutions can create a culture of integrity that discourages cheating and encourages ethical behavior. This approach not only reduces academic misconduct but also fosters a more positive and supportive academic environment. Tracking changes in peer influence throughout a student's educational journey can help teachers and policymakers develop targeted interventions to promote positive peer relationships, academic integrity, and student success. By understanding how peer influence evolves over time, schools can create supportive environments that foster healthy social interactions and academic growth.

5.1 Recommendations

- i Involve students in promoting academic integrity through peer-led programs or honor codes. This encourages students to hold each other accountable for maintaining examination integrity.
- ii Recognize and reward students who demonstrate ethical behavior and contribute to a culture of academic honesty.
- iii Ensure that disciplinary actions are fair and consistent across all students, fostering a sense of justice and accountability.

5.2 Suggestions for Future Research

- i Impact of School Culture on Examination Integrity

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